

Code of Conduct

NASIG is dedicated to providing a harassment-free conference experience for everyone, regardless of gender, gender identity and expression, age, sexual orientation, disability, physical appearance, body size, race, ethnicity, national origin, religion, or economic status. We do not tolerate the harassment of NASIG members and others who participate in NASIG conferences, events, meetings, conference sponsored social activities and online spaces in any form. Sexual language and imagery are not appropriate for any venue, including talks, workshops, receptions, Twitter and other online media, unless it is specifically relevant to the research being presented. Conference participants violating these rules may be sanctioned or expelled from the conference without a refund at the discretion of the conference organizers.

Harassment includes, but is not limited to:

- Verbal comments that reinforce social structures of domination related to gender, gender identity and expression, age, sexual orientation, disability, physical appearance, body size, race, ethnicity, national origin, or religion (or lack thereof)
- Sexual images in public spaces (unless it is specifically relevant to the research being presented)
- Deliberate intimidation, stalking, or following
- Harassing photography or recording
- Sustained disruption of talks or other events
- Inappropriate or unwelcome physical contact
- Unwelcome sexual attention
- Advocating for, or encouraging, any of the above behavior

Enforcement

Participants asked to stop any harassing behavior are expected to comply immediately.

Speakers, presenters, and exhibitors are also subject to the code of conduct.

If a participant engages in harassing behavior, NASIG retains the right to take any actions to keep the conference a welcoming environment for all participants. This includes warning the offender or expelling the offender from the conference with no refund.

NASIG may take action to redress anything designed to, or with the clear impact of, disrupting the conference or making the environment hostile for any participants.

Conference participants are expected to respect this policy at all conference venues and conference-related social activities.

Serious violations may result in inability to attend future conferences or ability to participate in NASIG activities. Persons who have been expelled or denied access may appeal to the NASIG Board.

Reporting

Harassment and other code of conduct violations reduce the value of our conference for everyone. If you are being harassed, notice that someone else is being harassed, if someone makes you or anyone else feel

unsafe or unwelcome, or if you have any other concerns, please contact a member of the Board as soon as possible. Board members can be identified by the flag on their badges. You can make a report either personally or anonymously.

If you feel that you are in immediate danger at any time during a NASIG Conference or event, contact law enforcement (by dialing 911) or the facility front desk without delay.

Anonymous Report

You can make an anonymous report at <https://goo.gl/zzJN30>. We can't follow up an anonymous report with you directly, but we will fully investigate it and take whatever action possible to prevent a recurrence.

Personal Report

You can make a personal report by:

Calling or messaging this phone number: (804) 322-9326. This phone number will be continuously monitored for the duration of the conference.

Contacting a Board member (via CPC at the registration desk or identified by flags on the name tags).

When taking a personal report, the Board member will ensure you are safe and cannot be overheard. They may involve other Board members to ensure your report is managed properly. Once safe, we'll ask you to tell us about what happened. This can be upsetting, but we'll handle it as respectfully as possible, and you can bring someone to support you. You won't be asked to confront anyone and we won't tell anyone who you are.

We will be happy to help you contact hotel/venue security, local law enforcement, and local support services; provide escorts; or otherwise assist you to feel safe for the duration of the event.

We expect participants to follow these rules at all conference venues, conference-related social events, and any other NASIG spaces or events.

This policy is primarily based on:

- http://geekfeminism.wikia.com/wiki/Conference_anti-harassment/Policy
- http://code4lib.org/conference/2014/code_of_conduct

Additional modifications inspired by:

- <http://www2.archivists.org/statements/saa-code-of-conduct>
- <http://www.wiscon.info/rules.php>